

ADVANCES IN NANOSTRUCTURED STRONTIUM TITANATE: SYNTHESIS AND CHARACTERIZATION

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ABSTRACT:

The synthesis and characterization methods of Strontium titanate nanoparticles are presented in this paper using several approaches. Different synthesis methods with the use of titanium and strontium salts as starting elements (precursor), chelating agents and pH variation are covered in this paper. Several techniques for characterisation like Transmission electron microscopy (TEM), Scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and X-ray diffraction (XRD) are adopted to examine the morphological, structural and chemical properties of the SrTiO₃. This review paper discusses the advantages as well as challenges of each synthesis technique and gives clarity for the optimal conditions for achieving high-quality SrTiO₃ nanoparticles.

Keywords: SrTiO₃; perovskite; nanoparticles; synthesis; characterization

1. INTRODUCTION

In a contemporary society, life without electronic appliances is inconceivable. The electromagnetic behaviour of the electronic equipment's and their components when scrutinized resulted in the need of double-function devices having capacitive properties [1]. Certain perovskite oxides possess capacitive properties and work as electrode material. Some of the common perovskite oxides are Lanthanum-based perovskite oxides, Strontium-based perovskite oxides, Cerium-based perovskite oxides and many more [2]. Strontium Titanate (SrTiO₃) is one of the perovskite oxides having general formula ABO₃ where A and B are cations and O is the anion in the compound.

SrTiO₃ have a distinguished cubical crystal structure in which Sr atom is at origin(A-site), Ti (B-site cation) is at the body center and three oxygen atoms at the three face centers forming an

octahedral coordination around Ti^{4+} . [3] It is an n-type semiconductor having flexible structure, good stability, non-toxic behavior and has amazing photocatalytic activity [4]. Its physical properties are completely dependent on its composition, shape, structure, size and crystal nature [5]. It has space group of $Pm\bar{3}m$ and a lattice parameter $a = 3.90528 \text{ \AA}$ at $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ [6]. The flower-shaped particle form of $SrTiO_3$ has more photocatalytic activity than cubical and spherical shapes of $SrTiO_3$. Its flower shaped structure has sharp edges and corners due to which it can possess large amount of energy and increased reactivity and photocatalytic activity. This property lacks in cubical shaped $SrTiO_3$ due to its flat, smooth and large surface area as reported by Lai, *et al* in the year 2015.

Studies related to $SrTiO_3$ is gaining acceptance worldwide due to its extraordinary properties like increased storage capacity, insulative property, optical transparency and chemical stability. This multifunctional perovskite (*due to its peculiar charge ordering in low d-electron occupancy however, charge ordering occurs mostly in doped systems with high d-electron*) is mostly utilized in the fabrication of electrical devices, solar cells (serving as a photo-anode for quantum dot-sensitized applications), and electro ceramics. The synthesis of strontium titanate nanoparticles has got special attention as compared to their counterparts due to its useful applications such as capacitors, thermistors, multilayer capacitors and optoelectronics devices [5].

This class of electronic materials possess voltage-sensing capabilities, exhibit high relative permittivity (dielectric constant), demonstrate minimal dielectric loss, and maintain stability over temperature and frequency variations. It shows dual-function qualities and are highly beneficial [1].

There are several methods by which $SrTiO_3$ can be synthesized, comprises of techniques such as solvothermal, sol-gel, solid-state reactions, molten salt synthesis, Sono chemical method, hydrothermal method, Combustion method, Co-precipitation method and many more [7]. Out of different synthesis methods, the sol-gel method is feasibly adopted, as this technique control the stoichiometric ratios which give highly pure nano-crystalline $SrTiO_3$ with controlled particle size and morphology. Moreover, this process requires low temperature while calcination, easier doping, high productivity, and the result obtained is a homogeneous and fine powder [1].

The various methodologies for the synthesis of $SrTiO_3$ nano-structures along with its characterization techniques is being discussed in this article.

2. METHODOLOGY

There are different methods to prepare perovskite oxides. Each method has its own advantages and limitations [8].

2.1 Solid State reaction

It is a traditional method used for preparing nanomaterials which involves various steps from mixing raw materials and calcinating them at different temperatures and to obtain the desired perovskite [8].

This method involves the precursors to react chemically even in the absence of any kind of solvent. The absence of solvent makes the synthesis cost effective and results in enhanced productivity. Hence this techniques is mostly preferred in industries as compared to other synthesis methods. In this “solventless” reaction, there is zero waste left to be remove at the final stage and thus this reaction is also called environmentally friendly synthesis method [7].

Advantages

1. It does not need costly appliances.
2. The equipment used in this method for e.g. Heating containers, oven etc. are durable.
3. To obtain the solids from reactants is easy because they are mostly in native condition and can be used as it is without further purification.
4. This method is applicable in industries and labs as it is easy to obtain the product from its reactants.
5. This technique results in products like metal oxides, sulfides and many more.
6. The quantity of products obtained is of similar quantity as that of the precursors used if the reaction is carried out for a longer time [9].

Disadvantages

1. The major drawback in this reaction is due to diffusion among solid materials.
2. The grinding and compression of the solid pellets which cause dispersion or diffusion of molecules makes the reaction time consuming and releases excess heat.
3. The impurities obtained along with the resulting product are though detectable, but difficult to eliminate [9].

2.2 Mechanical Milling Method

It is a simple method which can be performed with solid state or without using solid state reaction. This process involves the precursors and some suitable reactants to finish the solid state reaction to give the required composition of the nanomaterial, and process control solutions (Scheme 1). The final products obtained are of wide size distribution and transformable shape which has impurities and defects and therefore these techniques cannot be used for precise applications [10].

Scheme 1: Scheme of milling to prepare nanoparticles

M.H. El-Sadek *et al.* in their work reported that cubic SrTiO_3 particles of 70-100 nm crystalline size can be synthesized using mechanical activation-assisted solid-state reactions. Celestite (SrSO_4) and rutile (TiO_2) were thermally treated at a temperature of 1000°C in an inert atmosphere which resulted in 97% product. The whole process was supervised using different characterization methods namely thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), X-ray diffraction (XRD) and field emission scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Through Energy Dispersive X-Ray Spectroscopy (EDS). It was found that the atomic percentage of Strontium, Titanium, and Oxygen in the final compound was similar with the SrTiO_3 chemical formula. The mechanical activation technique requires high energy as the process was carried out at the temperature of approximate 1000°C which may result in distortion in the crystal structure.

The reaction was slow and inefficient, requiring an inert atmosphere (argon) to produce a product. However, M.H. El-Sadek *et al.* did not discuss that how impurities from celestite or rutile can influence the properties. [11]

2.3 Hydrothermal process

Hydrothermal word gets its origin from a Greek word “hydrous and thermal” hydrous meaning water and “thermal means heat. In the modern era, scientists have obtained various products through this process like ceramics and oxides. This method happens in hermetically sealed vessel in which temperature should be more than 25°C and pressures should be more than 0.1 MPa. The solvent inside the vessel can be saturated or non-saturated. This method can be carried out in mild conditions usually less than 350°C and at pressure of 50 MPa. The method is cost effective and consumes less energy. Recent research tells that oxide and non-oxide matter can be made keeping the temperature less than 200°C and pressure under 1.5 MPa. Due to improvement in reactor technology this method is now cost effective, and ceramic stuffs can be made in single step. [12]. This method is also used for the preparation of perovskite nanoparticles due to its synergetic effects from solvent, pressure and temperature, which results in stable final products [8].

K. S. Kiran in his work confirmed that Strontium titanate (SrTiO_3) nano cubes were synthesized through this process. The nanoparticles were formed cubically shaped, uniform and crystalline which has an average size of 18 nm when X- Ray Diffraction (XRD), Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) were performed. The synthesized SrTiO_3 nanoparticles showed excellent photodegradation property upon dyes (Methylene Blue (MB) and Tartrazine (TZ)) when illuminated by UV light and shows efficiency of 78.9% MB degradation and 76.4% TZ degradation with the reaction rates of $3.713 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$ and $3.56 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$. Their small size, high crystal system makes nano cubes appropriate specially in treatment of wastewater and photocatalytic environmental remedial approaches like air purification (photocatalytic filters) and hydrogen production. The crystal nature of Strontium titanate nano cubes was similar with the standard SrTiO_3 after the XRD characterization was performed.[13]

2.4 Sol- gel method

This method is the easiest method used in preparing highly pure nano and microstructures. It has many advantages as compared to other methods like stoichiometric control on the size, texture, surface properties of the materials, purity of material, low cost with highly pure product and many more [14]. It produces materials with large surface areas. This versatility of method makes it famous in nanoscale powders production [15]. The materials obtained has large surface to volume ratio.

The following figure represents the steps involved in sol- gel method:

Fig1: Steps involved in Sol gel method

The sol-gel synthesis of SrTiO_3 nanoparticles involves the preparation of a sol containing starting materials strontium and titanium after which gelation, drying and calcination is carried out (Fig.1). Different authors synthesized SrTiO_3 using different strontium precursors ($\text{Sr}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, $\text{SrCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Sr}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$), other titanium precursors ($\text{Ti}(\text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{O})_4$), chelating agents (acetic acid), and pH adjustment using NaOH . The choice of precursors and synthesis conditions affects the purity of phase, morphology and crystallinity of the product for example while using strontium precursors the pure crystalline SrTiO_3 was obtained at 500°C calcination temperature and Ra(fuel content ratio of citric acid:metal nitrate) of 3:1 was good to obtain pure state confirmed by XRD. Using acetic acid as chelating agent, pure SrTiO_3 perovskite structure was obtained at 600°C , while lower temperatures showed traces of SrC_2O_4 and anatase TiO_2

[16] [17][18]. Jinpeng Liu *et al.* reported Optimal energy storage performance achieved at 650°C annealing temperature through sol gel method.[19]

2.5 Solvothermal method

This approach resembles the hydrothermal approach in certain ways. In hydrothermal method, water is used as the solvent but the solvothermal method uses a variety of solvents, including alcohols, ketones, carboxylic acids, and toluene. This technique uses an organic solvent with a high boiling point and a low dielectric constant to produce nanoparticles of comparable sizes.[7]

When this method is carried out using alcohol as solvent it is known as alcohothermal method and if we use glycerol as solvents, it is known as glycothermal method. In this method, the reaction mixture is kept in sealed container, for example bomb or autoclave machine due to which the reaction speed increases and presence of solvent dissolve the solids present in the container.

The benefit of this method is that any substance can be dissolved in solvents used during this method just by raising the temperature and pressure to its core(critical)point.[20]

Nakashima *et al* in year 2013 reported, successful preparation of SrTiO₃ nanoparticles by using same method in which a mixture of 2-methoxy ethanol as absolute alcohol was used as the solvent which was able to control the shape and size of particle. Moreover, spherical, cubic and flake-like shaped SrTiO₃ particles were successfully made by solvo thermal method using mixtures of water/polyols as solvent. Solvent effect of glycol was found to be the main factor in maintaining the shape and size of particle.[21]

2.6 Molten Salt synthesis

It is a simple and flexible method for making perovskite oxide powders. It is a low cost and envi-friendly method used for green chemistry through which we get homogeneous compositions, perfect morphology and purified perovskite oxide nano powders.[22] This method needs low temperature and takes less preparation time [23]. This method can be carried out in regular chemistry labs and does not require any specific appliances. The chemical used in this method are cheap (Fig.2).

Fig. 2: Stages of molten salt synthesis method

Although this method is cost effective and gives pure and well-defined product still removal of salts from the product at final stage is quite challenging and difficult as it effects properties of final product. To carry out this method, using correct salt is essential as some salts can affect the environment in terms of disposal and toxicity, for example in acidic salts like Aluminum trichloride (AlCl_3) and alkalis like KOH salts close awareness is required due to its destructive nature and metals salts like barium chloride are harmful for human beings. Most importantly, it produces NO_2 and SO_2 gases at the stage of salt melting which a threat.[24]

Li, *et al* in the year 2010 reported preparation of SrTiO_3 by this method in which single phase SrTiO_3 was obtained in pure condition with no impurity.[25]

Wang, *et al* in year 2019 also reported that a cubic structured SrTiO_3 was prepared with molten chloride salt method at temperature of 974°C . [26]

2.7 Polymeric Precursor Method

The Pechini-type reaction is the foundation of this polymeric Precursor method.[27] In this method, chemical reaction occurs between metal ionic precursor, a stabilizing agent (Ethylene glycol) and a complexing agent (citric acid) which create a polymeric gel as a product. The metal ions get stuck(immobilized) in gel and get burned off. [29]

A cubic crystalline SrTiO_3 was made by this method using aluminum and praseodymium calcined for 2 hours at 800°C . A red colour emission was obtained at 617nm wavelength due to radioactive decay (from $1D_2 \rightarrow 3H_4$ transition of Pr^{3+}) During the method, there were certain limitations like oxygen atoms were not present which affected the material's growth, spreading of aluminum and praseodymium(Fig.3). Luminescent and structural properties of material also got affected. This process requires high control over the ratio of aluminum and praseodymium with exact conditions, if not maintained can lead impure product.[28]

Fig.3: Advantages and Disadvantages of low temperature reactions

2.8 Gel- combustion method

This method is a combination of combustion reactions and sol gel method. In this method, the precursors material is mixed with fuel like urea, glycine etc and then self-combustion takes place. It is a quick reaction which gives pure material but during this reaction one must keep safety in mind as this process release NO_x toxic gas and stoichiometric control can be challenging. This method is not suitable for making non oxide ceramic.[29]

Strontium titanate was made using sol gel combustion method by using citric acid in molar ration from 1:1 to 1:3 of metal nitrate and citric acid. Pure crystalline material was obtained at ratio 1:3 with particle size 45nm and with ratio 1:1 it was 40nm. With the increased ratio the material's dielectric properties got affected. Calcination at 500°C gave

best result confirmed from XRD. Particle with 7.5nm was obtained after being treated with acid at 600°C confirmed through XRD. [30]

2.9 Co-precipitation method

Another method for preparing metal oxide nanostructure is co precipitation method in which a homogenous solution of metal ions and water is mixed with precipitating agent typically a base like NaOH which form nanoparticles oxides which are followed by aging and stirring to form nanoparticles with no defects. Later on, after washing (to remove impurities) it is dried and calcined to get the final product.[31] .Through this method single and more than one component metal oxides can be made. This method has the ability to make particles of the required shape or size if some conditions with utmost carefulness are followed like pH of solution, temperature of reaction, rate of stirring and concentration of metal and salts can be controlled.[32] SrTiO₃ was synthesized by this method using Manganese (Mn) as dopant. Authors observed that chemical bonding, microstructure and photolytic activity of SrTiO₃ was affected by varying concentration of Mn ((x = 0.05–0.2). The process was carried out for the degradation of methylene blue in wastewater. The best form was obtained at x=0.15 concentration on Mn with the degradation rate of 54.69% under for UV irradiation till 5 h. The high crystalline material was obtained successfully confirmed by XRD, FTIR and using UV Spectrometer.[33] Synthesis of SrTiO₃ by other methods are summarised in the table below(Table 1) :

Table:1

Various methods of preparation of SrTiO₃ nanoparticles

Method	Observation	Reference
Pulsed wire discharge (PVD)	Reactants, chemical calculation(stoichiometry) of SrTiO ₃ was affected by PLD method used for thin layer deposition specially in ultraviolet light. in situ impedance spectroscopy was used to tap the changes occurring in conductivity. Under UV light more oxygen was absorbed by the reactants due to which conductivity increased.	[34]
Reverse Micelles	The size of particle and morphology was controlled when reverse micelles method was used as nanoreactors to make SrTiO ₃ . Spherical shape grains of SrTiO ₃ of size of 30nm–40	[35]

	nm was obtained. At 100 kHz, SrTiO ₃ show the dielectric constant of 90nm. Titanium isopropoxide (Ti[OCH(CH ₃) ₂] ₄) and glacial acetic acid was used in this process.	
Microwave Synthesis	SrTiO ₃ nano cuboids were prepared using microwave synthesis method in which titanium(IV) bis(ammonium lactato) dihydroxide was used as precursor. In comparison to other traditional methods nano cuboids were made more quickly through this method by heating the mixture at temperature 200 ⁰ C for about 8 hours. These nano cuboids can be used for the application of electronic and catalytic application like renewing plastics.	[36]

3. Characterization methods

a. X-Ray Diffraction(XRD)

b. Scanning Electron Microscopy(SEM)

c. Transmission Electron Microscopy Imaging (TEM)

Fig.4: Common techniques used for Characterization of SrTiO₃

Purity of SrTiO₃ nanoparticles can't be understood until and unless its results match the actual standards. To understand their structural, thermal and morphological properties, the following techniques are commonly used and its pictorial representation is given in Fig. 4. Besides this other methods are also used to characterize the material. To name a few, Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS), Nanoparticle tracking analysis (NTA) and many more.[37]

4. RESULTS

Synthesis of SrTiO₃ nanoparticles using different methods gives different results in terms of phase purity, crystallinity, and morphology. Characterization techniques such as XRD, SEM and TEM confirm the successful synthesis of high-quality SrTiO₃ nanoparticles with controlled particle size and morphology.

Single phase cubical SrTiO₃ with lattice parameter of 3.8843 Å was prepared by isothermal heating at 900°C for 2 hours with Mechanical milling method with the use of purified celestite concentrate (SrSO₄). The XRD result of synthesized SrTiO₃ shows that during transformation between SrSO₄ (Celestite) into SrCO₃ (Strontium Carbonate), SrSO₄ peaks got vanished. Furthermore, after 16 hours milling of the stoichiometric mixture of SrCO₃ and TiO₂ cubic perovskite structure SrTiO₃ was formed.[38]

Fibrous SrTiO₃ particles were prepared using strontium hydroxide octahydrate (Sr (OH)₂·8H₂O) and protonic layered tetra titanate (H₂Ti₄O₉) as precursors by Hydrothermal reaction method with crystalline size of 100nm at temperature 225°C confirmed from XRD results. This fibrous SrTiO₃ synthesized by this method has shown 1.5 times larger photolytic activity under UV light ($\lambda > 290$ nm) in comparison to SrTiO₃ powder. The fibrous morphology was detected by using SEM

which reveals that the fibers were distributed evenly and due to which photocatalytic activity of material got enhanced. [39]

SrTiO₃ was synthesized using two methods, in gelation (internal gelation) and gel combustion method. These sample were doped with Hf by using time-differential perturbed angular correlation (TDPAC) technique and X-ray diffraction (XRD) technique to study the morphological conditions at cationic sites of Titanium. The XRD results of the sample shown that the sample made by gel combustion method produced cent percent cubical structure in comparison to in-gelation method. Sample made by in gelation method contained 80.1% SrTiO₃ and 19.9% TiO₂ rutile impurity confirmed by Rietveld analysis. [40]

Another, Spin coating method was used for the fabrication of SrTiO₃ thin films with Strontium titanate solution as precursor. In this method, 25 layers of the precursor was deposited on substrate and the entire method was carried out using sol gel method. The XRD results shown the strong crystallinity in 25-layer sample. The highest peak intensities were at 32°, 40°, 47°, and 58°, which gets align with crystallographic planes (110), (111), (200), and (210). This 25-layer sample has shown its highest thickness of 224 nm and high absorption intensity. Microcracks and flaking defects were also observed in 25-layer sample when SEM was done.[41]

Another, Lanthanum Doped Strontium Titanate nanomaterial was prepared by using sol gel method for Photocatalytic and Supercapacitor applications with Strontium nitrate (Sr(NO₃)₂) and lanthanum nitrate (La(NO₃)₃) salts as precursors. In this method, precursors were dissolved in a solution of titanium tetra butoxide (Ti(OC₄H₉)₄) and to attain the molar ratio of 2:1 citric acid was also used. The XRD studies confirmed the cubical structure of size 22.2 nm and lattice parameter of 3.9126 Å with band energy gaps (E_g) of 3.4 eV. This rare earth doped perovskite Sr_{0.9}La_{0.1}TiO₃ nanomaterial shown larger surface area and enhanced charge storage capacity. TEM findings confirmed the well-defined lattice fringes, with successful doping of lanthanum with improved its supercapacitors properties.[42]

5 CONCLUSION

Different synthesis approaches, including the use of various strontium and titanium precursors, pH variation, and chelating agents, offer unique advantages and limitations. Characterization techniques such as XRD, SEM and TEM provide valuable information about the structural, morphological properties of the synthesized nanoparticles. This review paper explored the various methods of synthesis for the preparation of Strontium titanate (SrTiO₃). SrTiO₃

nanoparticles are obtained by different methods like, solid state reaction, mechanical milling method, hydrothermal process, sol gel method, solvothermal method, molten salt synthesis, Polymeric precursor method, gel combustion method and many more. Various characterization techniques were used to characterize Strontium titanate nanoparticles are X ray diffraction (XRD), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and transmission electron microscopy (TEM). Although many researchers have explored on synthesis and characterization of SrTiO₃, still there is a need of more research and a deeper focus on their applications particularly.

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